

FOCUS CHARACTERIZATION AT PALS

SUMMARY

Šimon Jelínek (jelinek@pals.cas.cz), Roman Dudžák,
Jan Dostál, Věra Hájková, Libor Juha,
Michal Krupka, Vojtěch Vozda, Jaromír Chalupský
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References

- **All versions of this document**

- <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18804275>

- **PALS**

- Title: The Prague Asterix Laser System

- <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1350569>

- **Beam characterization at PALS (@1315 nm without RPP)**

- Title: Retrieving the Phase of High-Power Laser Beams by Sequential Multi-Plane Imaging of the Focal Region

- <https://doi.org/10.1017/hpl.2026.10125>

PALS laser and focusing

- $\lambda_{1\omega} = 1315 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{3\omega} = 438 \text{ nm}$
- Pulse length FWHM $\sim 300 \text{ ps}$
- Energy on target up to $\sim 700 \text{ J}$

- Aspheric BK7 lens + 8 mm plan glass
- Collimated beam diameter = 290 mm
- Focal length $_{1\omega} = 627 \text{ mm}$
- Focal length $_{3\omega} = 600 \text{ mm}$

<https://www.avcr.cz/cs/veda-a-vyzkum/aktuality/Laser-PALS-vypalil-jiz-50-000.-vystrel>

Focus at PALS

Top view of chamber

Side view of chamber

FOCUS CHARACTERIZATION METHODS

Far-field imaging onto camera

- Laser beam is fully amplified and attenuated by 6 Large absorption ND filters ($\varnothing = 350$ mm), then it is focused, further attenuated only at 3ω by ND filters (50x50 mm, thickness = 3.73 mm), imaged by Microscope objective (Mitutoyo, $f = 4$ mm, or 10 mm), attenuated by Small absorption ND filters (50x50 mm), imaged onto NIR or VIS sensitive camera

Far-field imaging onto camera

Focusing lens

Microscope objective
($f = 4 \text{ mm}$, or 10 mm)

Neutral density optical filters

Camera

Ablation imprints

Characterize laser focus from damage induced on target by ablation (ablation imprints)

Direct method
Sub- μm resolution

Ex-situ analysis
Many shots

Ablation imprints example (3ω)

f ... normalized fluence

1 ω – 1315 nm

1 ω – log plot

- Far-field imaging
- Reference: Looking with the beam

A_{eff} [μm^2]
Effective area
29

F_{peak} [J/cm^2]
Peak fluence
 2.4×10^9

$F_{\text{peak}}/\tau_{\text{eff}}$ [W/cm^2]
Peak intensity
 6.9×10^{18}

$$\text{Fluence}_{\text{peak}} = \text{Energy}_{\text{pulse}}/A_{\text{eff}}$$

$$(\text{E}_{\text{pulse}} = 700 \text{ J})$$

$$(\tau_{\text{eff}} = 350 \text{ ps}, \tau_{\text{FWHM}} = 300 \text{ ps})$$

1 ω – linear plot

- Far-field imaging
- Reference: Looking with the beam

A_{eff} [μm^2]
Effective area
29

F_{peak} [J/cm^2]
Peak fluence
 2.4×10^9

$F_{\text{peak}}/\tau_{\text{eff}}$ [W/cm^2]
Peak intensity
 6.9×10^{18}

$$\text{Fluence}_{\text{peak}} = \text{Energy}_{\text{pulse}}/A_{\text{eff}}$$

$$(\text{E}_{\text{pulse}} = 700 \text{ J})$$

$$(\tau_{\text{eff}} = 350 \text{ ps}, \tau_{\text{FWHM}} = 300 \text{ ps})$$

Approximation for simulation

- Sum of two Gaussian beams
- $F(r) = F_0 \left[0.9699 \exp\left(-\frac{r^2}{a_1^2}\right) + (1 - 0.9699) \exp\left(-\frac{r^2}{a_2^2}\right) \right]$
- $a_1 = 2.4 \mu\text{m}$, $a_2 = 11 \mu\text{m}$

#61956
(26.11.2024)

Power profiles examples

Laser pulse number	Time range [ns]	Pulse energy [J]
59240	[-2.5, -1]	0.062
	[-1, -0.177]	39
	[-0.177, 0.152]	320
	[0.152, 0.8]	78

Pulse energies of the two chosen laser pulses in different parts of the power distributions. Time zero corresponds to the pulse peak.

Laser pulse number	Time range [ns]	Pulse energy [J]
58453	[-5, -2.4]	0.088
	[-2.4, -0.7]	6
	[-0.7, -0.132]	76
	[-0.132, 0.156]	484
	[0.156, 0.8]	130

1 ω – 1315 nm
With Random Phase Plate (RPP)

1 ω with Random Phase Plate

Quick summary

- A flat-top beam with diffracted area around it
- Sum of **2 supergaussian beams is the best fit** to the measured data ([link](#))
- **Supergaussian fit (flat-top) with adjusted pulse energy** is also reasonable ([link](#)) – **FWHM = 95 μm** , **pulse energy = 73 %** of pulse energy in the chamber

Beam profile measurement

- Measured by far-field imaging
- RPP focus position is in the position of the Hartmann focus position

This is what camera sees (I'm looking opposite the beam propagation direction)

With Random Phase Plate – log

With Random Phase Plate – linear

2D profile into 1D functions to fit

Sum up columns
Sum up rows

Most accurate approximation

Profile fitted by a sum of two supergaussian beams
(Minimization of normalized chi-squared)

Linear scale

Log scale

Different x axis range

Most accurate approximation

Profile fitted by a sum of two supergaussian beams

Energy corresponding to this beam description is **100%** of the pulse energy in the chamber

Equation of normalized fluence profile

$$f(r) = f_1 * \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{r - r_c}{w_1}\right)^{n_1}\right\} + (1 - f_1) * \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{r - r_c}{w_2}\right)^{n_2}\right\}$$

f1	0.886358
w1 (um)	49.71224
n1	5.974712
w2 (um)	82.54375
n2	1.307562
r_c (um)	0
A_eff (um2)	9446

$$F_{peak} = E_{pulse}/A_{eff}$$

Fitted 2D profile and original image, in scale

Supergauss approximation

Profile fitted with a supergaussian beam

Equation of normalized fluence profile

$$f(r) = \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{r - r_c}{w_1}\right)^{n_1}\right\}$$

w1 (um)	49.71224
n1	5.974712
r_c (um)	0
FWHM (um)	94.7
Aeff (um2)	6931

Energy corresponding to this beam description is 73% of the pulse energy in the chamber (73% = 6931/9446, ratio of effective areas)

Speckle characteristics

- Speckles inside the “inner focus” at half of peak fluence
 - 50 speckles
 - Average speckle area \pm standard deviation = $(4.4 \pm 3) \mu\text{m}^2$
- Peak fluence of speckles is approximately 2x the peak fluence of fitted beams

3 ω – 438 nm

Ablation imprints (3ω)

f ... normalized fluence

3 ω – upper estimate of focal spot

- ND filters had to be inserted between the lens and the focus position
- This enlarges the focus size significantly (from geometric optics)
- No measurement with far-field imaging

Upper estimate of the focal spot size (A_{eff})

A_{eff} [μm^2]
Effective area
300

F_{peak} [J/cm^2]
Peak fluence
 7×10^7

$F_{\text{peak}}/\tau_{\text{FWHM}}$ [W/cm^2]
Peak intensity
 2×10^{17}

$$Fluence_{\text{peak}} = Energy_{\text{pulse}}/A_{\text{eff}}$$

$$(E_{\text{pulse}} = 200 \text{ J})$$

$$(\tau_{1/e} = 180 \text{ ps}, \tau_{\text{FWHM}} = 300 \text{ ps})$$

3 ω – 438 nm
With Random Phase Plate (RPP)

3 ω with Random Phase Plate

Quick summary

- Middle of beam has slightly increased intensity
- Sum of **2 supergaussian beams is the best fit** to the measured data ([link](#))
- **Gaussian fit** with adjusted pulse energy is also **reasonable** ([link](#)) – **FWHM = 69 μm , pulse energy = 72 %** of pulse energy in the chamber

Beam profile measurement

- The beam fluence profile on the right is a combination of beam profile measured by far-field imaging (center) and cross-sections from ablation imprints (low fluence part), which are normalized by the far-field measurement
- **RPP focus position is 100 μm closer** to then lens than the Hartmann focus position (lens position needs to shift by -100 μm from Hartmann position)

This is what camera sees (I'm looking opposite the beam propagation direction)

Log plots

Ablation imprints and #60255

Ablation imprints and #60255

Linear plots

Ablation imprints and #60255

Ablation imprints and #60255

2D profile into 1D functions to fit

Most accurate approximation

Profile fitted by a sum of two supergaussian beams
(Minimization of normalized chi-squared)

Linear scale

Log scale

Different x axis range

Most accurate approximation

Profile fitted by a sum of two supergaussian beams

Energy corresponding to this beam description is **100%** of the pulse energy in the chamber

Equation of normalized fluence profile

$$f(r) = f_1 * \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{r - r_c}{w_1}\right)^{n_1}\right\} + (1 - f_1) * \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{r - r_c}{w_2}\right)^{n_2}\right\}$$

f1	0.98112
w1 (um)	41.57759
n1	2.39984
w2 (um)	199.8146
n2	1.85707
r_c (um)	0.00595
A_eff (um2)	7463.3

$$F_{peak} = E_{pulse}/A_{eff}$$

Fitted 2D profile and original image, in scale

Gauss approximation

Profile fitted with a Gaussian beam

Equation of normalized fluence profile

$$f(r) = \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{r - r_c}{w_1}\right)^{n_1}\right\}$$

w1 (um)	41.37
n1	2
r_c (um)	0
FWHM (um)	68.9
Aeff (um2)	5376

Energy corresponding to this beam description is 72% of the pulse energy in the chamber (72% = 5376/7463, ratio of effective areas)

Speckle characteristics

- 23 diameter measurements (of ca 12 speckles)
- I set threshold in ImageJ to be half of the highest value in the image, and I measured diameters of the thresholded areas
- Speckle diameter = **$(1.0 \pm 0.3) \mu\text{m}$**
- Peak fluence of speckles is approximately 2.1x the peak fluence of fitted beams

List of changes

- 13.1.2026
 - Used results with a calibrated camera
 - Presentation is online on Google Drive
- 26.2.2026
 - Slide 10, Slide 11: Corrected τ_{FWHM} to τ_{eff} in the intensity calculation
 - Slide 13: Added tables about partial energies in parts of power distribution
- 18.5.2026
 - Added References slide